

The Efficacy and Acceptance of Online Learning vs. Offline Learning in Higher Learning Institutions: A Systematic Review

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Abstract:

Overview: Online learning has emerged as a flexible and accessible alternative, allowing students to engage with course materials at their own pace and from various locations. This systematic review on the efficacy and acceptance of online versus offline learning in higher learning institutions revealed significant insights into the evolving landscape of education.

Body of Knowledge: The study explored the comparative effectiveness and receptiveness of online and traditional face-to-face learning modalities. It synthesized a wide range of empirical research to assess the educational outcomes, student satisfaction, and institutional acceptance of these two learning approaches.

Methods: The study employed both the qualitative and quantitative methods and a descriptive survey design that sampled faculty Heads of departments, Lecturers, and Students. The study was conducted from four higher learning institutions within Lusaka district of Zambia with a sample size of 100 respondents. Data was obtained from the respondents by means of interviews, surveys and questionnaires. The quantitative data collected through the questionnaires were analyzed using appropriate statistical methods, such as descriptive statistics using SPSS and Microsoft excel whereas the qualitative data from semi structured interviews were analyzed thematically.

Results: The findings revealed that online learning offers flexibility and accessibility, leading to enhanced student engagement and learning autonomy. However, challenges such as technological barriers, lack of face-to-face interaction, and varying levels of student self-discipline impact its efficacy. In contrast, offline learning continues to be valued for its structured environment and direct interaction, which are critical for collaborative learning and immediate feedback.

Recommendation: The study emphasized the need for strategic integration of both learning methods to optimize educational outcomes in higher learning institutions.

Keywords: Efficacy, Higher Education, Offline Learning, Online Learning, and Student Acceptance.

1. INTRODUCTION

A systematic review on the efficacy and acceptance of online learning versus offline learning in higher learning institutions reveals a nuanced landscape where both modes of education offer unique benefits and challenges. Online learning, characterized by its flexibility, accessibility, and potential for personalized learning experiences, has gained substantial acceptance, particularly in contexts where traditional classroom-based education is less feasible. However, its efficacy often hinges on the quality of course design, the availability of technological infrastructure, and the learners' self-discipline and motivation (Adzima, 2020). Conversely, offline learning, with its established structure, face-to-face interactions, and immediate feedback mechanisms, remains highly valued for fostering deep engagement, collaboration, and a sense of community among students (Chanda et al, 2024). The review highlights that while online learning can effectively complement and, in some cases, substitute offline learning, the optimal approach in higher education may lie in blended learning models that leverage the strengths of both formats. Ultimately, the acceptance of either mode depends significantly on the context, including cultural factors, the nature of the subject matter, the quality of education and the specific needs of the student population.

Higher education serves as a critical pillar in the development of individuals and societies, offering advanced knowledge, specialized skills, and the opportunity for intellectual growth. It plays a vital role in fostering innovation, driving economic growth, and promoting social mobility. Ngulube et al (2024)'s study noted that economic growth refers to the sustained increase in a country's productive capacity and output of goods and services over time, typically measured by the rise in real GDP. It's a multifaceted concept influenced by various factors such as technological advancements, capital accumulation, human capital development, institutional quality, and macroeconomic stability. In higher education institutions, students engage with complex ideas, develop critical thinking abilities, and prepare for careers that require specialized expertise. The importance of higher education has only grown in recent years, with the increasing demand for a highly educated workforce in a rapidly evolving global economy (Pascarella & Terenzini, 2005). Additionally, higher education institutions are increasingly integrating technology into their curricula, adopting blended learning models, and exploring the efficacy of online vs. offline learning to meet the diverse needs of students. As access to higher education expands, it continues to shape the future of societies by cultivating informed, skilled, and engaged citizens capable of contributing to national and global progress.

Student acceptance of online and offline learning in higher education is shaped by a variety of factors, including technological access, personal learning preferences, and perceived effectiveness. Pei & Wu (2019) indicated that while online learning offers flexibility and accessibility, students may initially struggle with self-discipline and the absence of face-to-face interactions, which are

crucial for building a sense of community and engagement. On the other hand, offline learning, characterized by traditional classroom settings, is often perceived as more structured and supportive, with direct access to instructors and peers. However, Chanda (2024) alluded that it may lack the flexibility that online learning provides, making it less appealing to students with demanding schedules or those who prefer a more self-paced learning environment. Ultimately, the acceptance of either mode depends largely on the individual student's circumstances, including their ability to adapt to different learning environments and their comfort level with technology.

Chanda et al (2024) pointed out that online learning in higher education has gained significant momentum in recent years, driven by advancements in technology and the need for flexible, accessible education. This mode of learning offers students the ability to access coursework, engage with instructors, and collaborate with peers from virtually anywhere, breaking down geographical and temporal barriers. The convenience of online learning appeals to a diverse student population, including working professionals, international students, and those with family obligations (Duan et al, 2021). However, the effectiveness of online learning depends heavily on the quality of instructional design, student engagement, and the availability of technological resources. While some studies highlight the potential of online learning to provide an equivalent or even superior educational experience compared to traditional in-person classes, others point to challenges such as reduced interpersonal interaction, the digital divide, and the need for self-discipline among students (Parisi et al, 2019). As higher education institutions continue to adapt to this mode of delivery, the focus is increasingly on creating robust support systems, integrating interactive elements, and ensuring that online education meets the rigorous standards of academic quality and student satisfaction.

Offline learning in higher education, often referred to as traditional or face-to-face learning, remains a cornerstone of academic instruction. It provides students with a structured environment where they can engage directly with instructors and peers, fostering a sense of community and collaboration. Chanda (2024) says that this mode of learning allows for real-time interaction, immediate feedback, and hands-on experiences, which can be crucial for disciplines that require practical application, such as laboratory work, field studies, and workshops. Moreover, offline learning environments often offer a more immersive experience, where students can participate in group discussions, seminars, and extracurricular activities, all of which contribute to a holistic educational experience. Despite the growing popularity of online learning platforms, offline learning continues to be valued for its ability to create a disciplined and focused atmosphere, where students can fully concentrate on their studies without the distractions that may accompany online environments (Gaber et al, 2020). Furthermore, the physical presence of educators and peers in a shared space can enhance motivation, accountability, engagement and quality of education

obtained, leading to potentially better academic outcomes. Chanda et al (2024)'s study revealed that quality education encompasses a holistic approach to learning, aiming to provide all students with the knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values necessary to lead productive and fulfilling lives. It ensures inclusive and equitable access to education, accommodating diverse learning needs and fostering an environment that encourages critical thinking, creativity, and lifelong learning.

1.2 Statement of the problem

The rapid evolution of educational technology has led to a significant increase in the adoption of online learning platforms alongside traditional offline learning methods in higher education institutions. Gupta & Kumar (2019) alluded that despite the growing prevalence of online learning, there remains a critical need to evaluate its efficacy and acceptance compared to conventional face-to-face instruction. The disparity in learning outcomes, engagement levels, and overall effectiveness between online and offline learning methods poses a challenge for educators, policymakers, and students (Zohaib et al, 2024). This study sought to address this issue through a systematic review, aiming to identify and analyze existing research on the comparative effectiveness of online and offline learning modalities. By synthesizing findings from various studies, the review provided a comprehensive understanding of how these learning methods impact academic performance, student satisfaction, and educational equity. This investigation may help inform best practices and guide future developments in educational technology and pedagogical strategies.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to systematically review and evaluate the efficacy and acceptance of online learning compared to traditional offline learning methods in higher education institutions. By synthesizing existing research, the study aimed to assess how well online learning platforms meet educational objectives and how they are perceived by students and educators relative to traditional classroom settings.

1.4 Objectives of the Study

- To evaluate the efficacy of online learning compared to offline learning in selected higher learning institutions within Lusaka district, Zambia.
- To assess the perceptions of online learning vs. offline learning among students and educators in selected higher learning institutions within Lusaka district, Zambia.

1.5 Theoretical Framework

The study was guided by the Blended Learning Theory. The theory integrates both online and offline learning modalities to create a more flexible and effective educational experience. In the context of higher learning institutions, this approach has gained prominence due to its potential to combine the strengths of traditional face-to-face instruction with the benefits of digital learning (Yang et al, 2021). A systematic review on the efficacy and acceptance of online versus offline learning highlights that blended learning can offer a more personalized and adaptive educational

experience. Online components provide students with access to a wealth of resources and facilitate asynchronous learning, allowing for greater flexibility and self-paced progress. Conversely, offline or face-to-face interactions foster immediate feedback, hands-on experiences, and enhanced interpersonal communication, which can be crucial for subjects requiring practical application and collaborative learning (Zhang et al, 2023). The review suggested that while online learning offers scalability and convenience, offline learning remains valuable for its direct engagement and support. The combined approach of blended learning aims to leverage the advantages of both methods, addressing individual learning preferences and needs while maintaining a structured and interactive educational environment. This integration often results in increased student satisfaction and improved learning outcomes, although its effectiveness can vary based on the specific implementation and the context of the educational institution.

1.5 Significance of the Study

The study's significance lies in its potential to inform educational practices and policies that can enhance student outcomes and institutional effectiveness. As higher education institutions increasingly adopt diverse learning modalities, understanding the comparative advantages and challenges of online and offline learning becomes crucial. This systematic review aimed to provide a comprehensive analysis of existing research on this topic, evaluating how online and offline learning environments impact student engagement, academic performance, and overall satisfaction. By identifying the strengths and limitations of each approach, this study may offer valuable insights for educators, administrators, and policymakers to make informed decisions about integrating technology into the curriculum. Additionally, it may address student preferences and barriers to access, contributing to the development of more effective and inclusive educational strategies that accommodate diverse learning needs and improve the quality of higher education.

2. METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a mixed methods approach which is a combination of quantitative and qualitative data. Exploratory and descriptive designs were as well considered appropriate as they also allowed for more flexible strategies of data collection in order to answer the research questions (Banda et al, 2017). The study was aimed at collecting information from respondents on the efficacy and acceptance of online learning vs. offline learning in higher learning institutions in the 4 selected higher learning institutions within Lusaka district in Zambia. Structured open-ended interviews were conducted, surveys and questionnaires were used to respondents to collect data. The sample consisted 100 respondents; 10% of the target population 1000. The population for the study was purposefully drawn from the 4 institutions. Purposive sampling procedure was used to select Faculty heads of departments (8); 2 representing each institution and lecturers (20); 5 representing each institution while the simple random sampling procedure was used to select the students (72); 18 representing each institution. The data collection process involved distributing the questionnaires to the selected participants and conducting individual interviews. The quantitative data collected through the questionnaires were analyzed using appropriate statistical

methods, such as descriptive statistics using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) and Microsoft excel whereas the qualitative data from semi structured interviews were analyzed thematically. The study avoided pressuring respondents to take part in the research. Alternatively, permission consents, assents were obtained from respondents involved in the research and the research topic was strategically selected to ensure that there was no harm whatsoever to the research respondents. The study also upheld research ethical considerations such as voluntary participation of the respondents, confidentiality, honesty, and right of privacy.

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Efficacy of Online Learning Compared to Offline Learning in Selected Higher Learning Institutions

According to research findings, the study identified five factors on efficacy of online learning compared to offline learning in selected higher learning institutions within Lusaka district. Technology and Resources was at 30%, Accessibility and Flexibility at 25%, Learning Outcomes and Performance at 20%, Cost and Efficiency at 15%, and Engagement and Interaction at 10%.

The study results noted that technology and resources play a crucial role in the efficacy of online learning compared to offline learning in higher learning institutions within Lusaka District. Online learning leverages a range of technological tools and platforms, such as Learning Management Systems (LMS), virtual classrooms, and multimedia content, to enhance the learning experience. Mumbi & Nyirenda (2024) noted that platforms and technologies such as student management systems, learning management systems and finance systems bridge the gap between the growing demand for higher education and the limited number of resources available, such as lecturers and classroom space. These resources enable flexible access to educational materials, facilitate real-time communication between students and instructors, and support diverse learning styles through interactive and multimedia elements. Additionally, online learning environments often incorporate advanced data analytics to monitor student progress and personalize learning experiences. In contrast, offline learning typically relies on traditional resources like textbooks, physical classrooms, and face-to-face interactions, which may limit accessibility and adaptability (Peng & Wang, 2022). While offline methods provide a structured environment and immediate support from instructors, they can be constrained by geographical and logistical challenges. The efficacy of online learning in Lusaka District, therefore, hinges on the effective integration of technology and resources to overcome these limitations and offer a more accessible, adaptable, and engaging educational experience (Chanda & Zohaib, 2024).

Furthermore, online learning offers significant advantages in terms of accessibility and flexibility, particularly when compared to traditional offline learning methods. In the context of higher learning institutions, online learning provides a more inclusive educational environment by allowing students to access course materials, lectures, and resources from any location with an internet connection (Cheng et al, 2023). This removes geographical and physical barriers, making

education more attainable for those who may face challenges in commuting or residing far from campus. Additionally, online learning platforms often incorporate asynchronous learning opportunities, enabling students to engage with content and complete assignments at their own pace. This flexibility supports diverse learning styles and schedules, accommodating students who may be balancing education with work or personal commitments. Conversely, offline learning, while valuable for its structured and immediate interpersonal interactions, can be limited by fixed schedules and physical attendance requirements, which may not suit all students' needs (Chanda, 2024). Therefore, the accessibility and flexibility inherent in online learning not only enhance educational reach but also adapt to the varied lifestyles and circumstances of students in Lusaka District, fostering a more equitable and responsive learning environment.

The findings also revealed that learning outcomes and performance are critical indicators for evaluating the efficacy of online learning compared to offline (traditional) learning in higher education. One of the lecturers explained that:

“Online learning offers flexibility, allowing students to access materials and engage with coursework at their convenience, which can enhance learning for those with varying schedules and commitments”.

This mode often incorporates diverse digital resources, interactive elements, and real-time feedback mechanisms that can enrich the educational experience. However, the effectiveness of online learning in achieving learning outcomes and performance improvements depends on factors such as the quality of digital content, the design of the online platform, and the level of student engagement (Gianoni-Capenakas et al, 2019). Conversely, offline learning provides structured face-to-face interactions and immediate support from instructors, which can be beneficial for building foundational skills and fostering deeper understanding through direct communication. Research suggests that while online learning can offer comparable or sometimes superior outcomes in terms of flexibility and resource availability, it may struggle with issues such as lower engagement levels and technical difficulties, which can affect overall performance. Offline learning, with its structured environment and personal interaction, may enhance motivation and participation, potentially leading to better performance in some cases (Chanda et al, 2024). Evaluations of learning outcomes and performance thus reveal that the efficacy of online versus offline learning is influenced by the specific institutional context, student needs, and the implementation of pedagogical strategies.

Faculty heads of departments alluded that in comparing the efficacy of online learning to offline learning in selected higher learning institutions, cost and efficiency are critical factors to consider. Online learning typically offers a more cost-effective solution by reducing the need for physical infrastructure and associated maintenance costs, such as classroom space, utilities, and on-campus resources. Additionally, it eliminates commuting costs for students and allows institutions to scale their offerings without proportional increases in physical resources (Hardré et al, 2010). However, the initial investment in technology and platform development can be significant. On the efficiency front, online learning provides flexibility that can lead to increased student engagement and

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learning outcomes. It allows for self-paced learning, which can accommodate diverse learning styles and schedules, potentially improving overall efficiency in content delivery and assessment. Despite these advantages, challenges such as technology access, digital literacy, and potential distractions at home can impact the effectiveness of online learning (Hodges et al, 2020). Conversely, offline learning, while often more resource-intensive, can benefit from face-to-face interactions that may enhance comprehension and retention through direct engagement with instructors and peers. Ultimately, the choice between online and offline learning involves balancing these cost and efficiency factors against the specific needs and capabilities of both students and institutions.

The respondents also pointed out that engagement and interaction are pivotal components in evaluating the efficacy of online learning compared to offline learning in higher education. Online learning platforms often leverage tools such as discussion forums, video conferencing, and interactive quizzes to foster engagement among students. Chanda & Siyunda (2023) added that these tools facilitate real-time interaction, enabling students to participate in discussions, collaborate on projects, and receive immediate feedback, which can enhance their learning experience. However, the effectiveness of these interactions can vary based on the design and implementation of the online learning environment. In contrast, offline learning traditionally emphasizes face-to-face interactions, where students engage directly with instructors and peers in physical classrooms. This setting allows for spontaneous dialogue, non-verbal communication, and immediate clarification of doubts, potentially leading to a richer learning experience (Braxton et al, 2000). Research suggests that while online platforms can offer flexible and convenient learning options, the depth of engagement and interaction in offline settings often provides a more immersive educational experience. Burgess et al (2018) noted that the challenge for online learning is to replicate or even surpass the interactive elements of offline learning, ensuring that students remain motivated and connected despite the physical distance.

Figure1: Efficacy of Online Learning Compared to Offline Learning in Selected Higher Learning Institutions

3.2. Perceptions of Online Learning vs. Offline Learning among Students and Educators in Selected Higher Learning Institutions

3.2.1. Students' Perceptions of Online Learning vs. Offline Learning in Selected Higher Learning Institutions

The findings on student perceptions of online vs. offline learning revealed that flexibility and convenience are central factors influencing student perceptions of online versus offline learning in higher learning institutions within Lusaka District. Online learning offers unparalleled flexibility, allowing students to access course materials, participate in discussions, and complete assignments on their own schedules, which can be particularly advantageous for those balancing studies with work or family commitments. This mode of learning also provides the convenience of participating from any location, reducing the need for physical travel and allowing for a more personalized learning environment (Zohaib et al, 2024). In contrast, offline learning, while often perceived as more structured and interactive, requires students to adhere to fixed class schedules and physically attend lectures, which can be less adaptable to individual needs (Xu et al, 2023). Students in Lusaka District have expressed that the ability to manage their

time more effectively and the reduction in commute time associated with online learning significantly enhance their overall educational experience. However, some students also appreciate the direct engagement and immediate feedback available in offline settings, which can foster a more connected and collaborative learning atmosphere. Wang et al (2023) alluded that balancing these perceptions involves weighing the benefits of flexible, self-paced study against the value of in-person interaction and structured classroom experiences.

The respondents noted that online learning often presents challenges related to engagement due to the absence of physical presence and real-time interaction, which can impact students' ability to participate actively and feel connected to their peers and instructors. Many students report that virtual environments can lead to feelings of isolation and disengagement, as online platforms may lack the immediacy and personal touch of face-to-face interactions (Watjatrakul, 2014). In contrast, offline learning environments tend to facilitate higher levels of direct engagement and interaction, allowing students to benefit from spontaneous discussions, group activities, and immediate feedback from instructors. This traditional format fosters a sense of community and collaborative learning that many students find motivating and supportive. However, offline learning also has its limitations, such as scheduling constraints and logistical challenges that can affect participation. Overall, while online learning offers flexibility and accessibility, its effectiveness in fostering engagement and interaction can be significantly influenced by the quality of digital tools and strategies used, as well as the ability of students and instructors to adapt to and manage the virtual learning environment effectively (Alma et al, 2024).

Additionally, learning outcomes are crucial in evaluating the effectiveness of both online and offline learning modalities. In the context of selected higher learning institutions within Lusaka District, student perceptions of these outcomes often reveal significant insights into their educational experiences. Online learning, characterized by its flexibility and accessibility, allows students to engage with course materials at their own pace, potentially enhancing their understanding and retention of knowledge (Allen & Seaman, 2017). However, it also presents challenges such as limited face-to-face interaction, which some students may perceive as a drawback in terms of collaborative learning and immediate feedback. One of the students narrated that:

“Offline learning, or traditional classroom-based instruction, is often valued for its structured environment and direct engagement with instructors and peers, which can foster a more interactive and supportive learning experience”.

Students might perceive offline learning as more effective for grasping complex concepts through in-person discussions and practical exercises. However, the rigid schedule and commuting requirements can be seen as constraints (Blythman & Orr, 2003). Overall, students' perceptions of learning outcomes in these two modalities reflect their personal learning preferences and experiences, highlighting the need for a balanced approach that leverages the strengths of both online and offline learning to optimize educational effectiveness in higher education institutions.

The study also revealed that technical issues significantly impact student perceptions of online learning compared to offline learning in higher learning institutions within Lusaka District. In online learning environments, students often face challenges such as inadequate internet connectivity, limited access to reliable technological devices, and frequent platform outages or technical glitches (Chanda et al, 2023). These issues can lead to interruptions in the learning process, decreased engagement, and frustration, thereby negatively affecting their overall experience and perception of online education. Conversely, offline learning, conducted in physical classrooms, typically offers a more stable and controlled environment where technical problems are less prevalent. However, offline learning may still encounter challenges such as overcrowded classes, inadequate learning materials, and limited access to technology for students from lower socioeconomic backgrounds (Chanda, 2024). The disparity in technical reliability between online and offline learning environments influences how students perceive the effectiveness and accessibility of each mode. Overall, while online learning presents innovative opportunities for education, its perceived effectiveness can be compromised by persistent technical issues, highlighting the need for improved infrastructure and support systems to enhance the learning experience for students (Bozkurt & Sharma, 2020).

Figure2: Students' Perceptions of Online Learning vs. Offline Learning

3.2.2. Educators' Perceptions of Online Learning vs. Offline Learning in Selected Higher Learning Institutions

The study results showed that teaching effectiveness in higher learning institutions often hinges on the educator's perception of online versus offline learning environments. In Lusaka District, Zambia, this perception is shaped by various factors such as engagement, accessibility, and the overall quality of education delivery. Educators who favor offline learning highlight the benefits of face-to-face interactions, which they believe foster better student-teacher relationships, immediate feedback, and a more controlled learning environment (Brown et al, 2018). They argue that offline settings facilitate hands-on activities, spontaneous discussions, and a more immersive learning experience. Conversely, those who support online learning emphasize its flexibility, which allows for accommodating diverse learning styles and schedules. They appreciate the ability to integrate multimedia resources, interactive tools, and scalable content delivery that can enhance student engagement and accessibility, particularly for those with geographical or time constraints. The perception of effectiveness often reflects a balance between these factors, with some educators advocating for a blended approach that combines the strengths of both modalities to optimize learning outcomes (Zenke et al, 2017). This dual perspective highlights the need for ongoing assessment and adaptation to ensure that both online and offline learning environments are leveraged to their full potential, considering the specific needs and contexts of the institutions and their students.

The findings also recorded that resource availability significantly influences educators' perceptions of online versus offline learning in higher learning institutions. Online learning environments often require a robust infrastructure, including high-speed internet, advanced digital tools, and reliable platforms for content delivery and interaction (Jenkins et al, 2023). Educators may view these needs as a challenge if institutions lack the necessary resources or if there are disparities in access among students. In contrast, offline learning typically relies on traditional resources such as textbooks, physical libraries, and in-person instructional materials. Educators may perceive offline learning as more straightforward due to the tangible nature of these resources and the established processes for their use. However, the perception of offline learning may also be constrained by limitations such as overcrowded classrooms, insufficient teaching materials, and logistical challenges (Chanda, 2023). Overall, educators' views on resource availability are shaped by their experiences with and expectations of both learning modalities, highlighting the importance of equitable resource distribution and support to enhance the effectiveness of either approach.

Additionally, educators' perceptions of online learning versus offline learning in higher learning institutions reveal a spectrum of challenges and solutions. A prominent challenge with online learning is the perceived lack of engagement and interaction, as educators worry about students' diminished motivation and participation in a virtual environment compared to face-to-face settings. One of the lecturers pointed out that:

“Technical issues, such as unreliable internet connections and inadequate digital infrastructure, further exacerbate these concerns, impeding the effectiveness of online delivery”.

Additionally, the absence of physical classroom dynamics can hinder the development of interpersonal skills and the immediate feedback loop that is often present in traditional settings. To address these issues, institutions can implement hybrid or blended learning models that combine the strengths of both online and offline approaches. By incorporating interactive elements such as virtual discussion forums, collaborative projects, and real-time feedback mechanisms, educators can enhance engagement and maintain a sense of connection among students (Chanda et al, 2024). Furthermore, investing in robust technical support and ensuring equitable access to digital resources can mitigate technical barriers. Professional development for educators is also crucial, equipping them with the skills to effectively design and deliver online content, and adapt their teaching strategies to suit diverse learning environments (Chan,2005). These solutions can help bridge the gap between online and offline learning, fostering a more effective and inclusive educational experience.

Figure3: Educators' Perceptions of Online Learning vs. Offline Learning

3.2.3. Institutional Perspectives of Online Learning vs. Offline Learning in Selected Higher Learning Institutions

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The results revealed that in the context of online learning, support and infrastructure play pivotal roles in determining the effectiveness and accessibility of educational programs. Online learning requires robust technological infrastructure, including reliable internet connectivity, modern computing devices, and efficient Learning Management Systems (LMS). Institutions in Lusaka District that have invested in these technologies tend to provide more seamless and interactive learning experiences for students. Access to high-speed internet is crucial, as it affects students' ability to engage with course materials, participate in virtual discussions, and complete online assessments (Kavi et al, 2019). Many institutions are working to improve this by partnering with internet service providers or investing in campus-wide Wi-Fi networks. In addition to physical infrastructure, institutional support systems are essential for online learning. This includes technical support teams that assist students and faculty with troubleshooting and system navigation. Mumbi & Nyirenda (2024) alluded that effective online learning programs also incorporate user-friendly LMS platforms that offer comprehensive resources such as lecture recordings, discussion forums, and interactive modules. Institutions providing training for both students and faculty on how to use these systems can significantly enhance the online learning experience. Furthermore, creating dedicated helpdesks or online support channels can provide immediate assistance and foster a supportive learning environment (LeCun et al, 2015).

Offline learning, while less dependent on digital infrastructure, still requires substantial institutional support and resources. Physical infrastructure, such as well-equipped classrooms, libraries, and laboratories, is fundamental to offline learning. Institutions need to ensure that these facilities are up-to-date and adequately maintained to support effective teaching and learning. For example, modern classrooms should be equipped with audio-visual aids, comfortable seating, and adequate lighting to facilitate interactive and engaging lessons. Support systems for offline learning include academic advising, library services, and extracurricular activities that enhance the educational experience (Lave & Wenger, 2015). Academic advisors play a critical role in guiding students through their coursework and career planning. Libraries need to provide access to a wide range of academic resources, including books, journals, and digital databases. Additionally, Chanda (2023)'s study noted that extracurricular activities and student support services, such as counseling and career services, contribute to a well-rounded educational experience. Comparing support and infrastructure between online and offline learning reveals distinct differences in the type of resources required. Online learning demands a strong technological backbone and digital support services, while offline learning relies more on physical facilities and personal support systems (Gulley & Mullendore, 2014). Institutions in Lusaka District that successfully integrate these elements can create more effective and inclusive learning environments, regardless of the mode of delivery.

Furthermore, effective implementation of online and offline learning requires thorough strategic planning. Institutions need to develop comprehensive strategies that consider the strengths and limitations of both modalities. For online learning, this involves selecting appropriate Learning

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Management Systems (LMS), ensuring adequate bandwidth and technical support, and integrating multimedia resources. On the other hand, offline learning strategies involve managing physical resources, scheduling classroom sessions, and fostering a conducive learning environment (Felicia et al, 2020). Institutions must align their strategic plans with their mission and vision, considering factors such as accessibility, equity, and quality of education. The success of both online and offline learning largely depends on the preparedness and adaptability of faculty members. Mpolomoka et al (2017) noted that institutions must invest in continuous professional development to equip educators with the necessary skills and knowledge. For online learning, this includes training on digital tools, online pedagogy, and virtual classroom management. Successful learning requires training on classroom engagement techniques, student assessment strategies, and traditional teaching methods (Mwila & Chanda, 2024). Institutions should provide ongoing support and resources to help faculty effectively transition between and integrate both learning modalities into their teaching practices. Both online and offline learning environments require tailored student support services. For online learning, institutions must offer resources such as virtual tutoring, online counseling, and technical assistance. Additionally, they should create mechanisms to ensure that students have access to necessary digital tools and a reliable internet connection. In offline learning settings, support services include in-person tutoring, academic advising, and campus-based facilities. Institutions must ensure that these support systems are equitable and accessible to all students, regardless of their mode of learning.

The findings further noted that institutions need robust mechanisms to evaluate the effectiveness and quality of both online and offline learning experiences. This involves setting clear benchmarks and performance indicators for each modality. For online learning, evaluation might include metrics such as student engagement, course completion rates, and feedback on digital tools (Muilenburg & Berge, 2005). Offline learning evaluations often focus on classroom interactions, student performance assessments, and overall learning outcomes. Institutions should use these evaluations to inform policy adjustments, improve teaching practices, and enhance the overall learning experience. The institutional culture plays a significant role in the successful implementation of online and offline learning. Chanda & Chitondo (2023) defines culture as a collaboration of shared meanings or common beliefs among an organization's members. Institutions with a culture that embraces innovation and flexibility are better positioned to integrate new learning modalities effectively. This includes fostering a collaborative environment where faculty, staff, and students can openly discuss and address challenges related to both online and offline learning. Institutions must be willing to adapt their policies and practices in response to feedback and emerging trends to ensure that they remain relevant and effective in meeting educational goals. Miller & Hafner (2008) says that by developing comprehensive policies, investing in faculty and student support, and maintaining a focus on evaluation and adaptability, institutions can effectively manage and optimize both learning modalities to enhance educational outcomes.

4. CONCLUSION

The study on the efficacy and acceptance of online learning versus offline learning in higher learning institutions reveals nuanced insights into the strengths and limitations of each modality. Online learning offers significant flexibility and accessibility, allowing students to engage with course materials and instructors from various locations and at their own pace, which can enhance learning opportunities for those with time constraints or geographical limitations. However, challenges such as technological barriers, lack of immediate feedback, and diminished interpersonal interactions can impact its effectiveness. Offline learning, on the other hand, provides structured environments and face-to-face interactions that can foster more direct engagement and immediate support, often leading to higher satisfaction among students who value in-person communication and hands-on experiences. The study highlighted that while both modes have their merits, the optimal learning experience may lie in a blended approach that combines the strengths of online flexibility with the personal engagement of offline methods. Ultimately, the acceptance and efficacy of each learning modality are influenced by factors such as individual learning preferences, the quality of course design, and the level of institutional support provided.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are actions that should be taken on the basis of the findings of this study;

1. Enhance Online Learning Platforms and Infrastructure:

- Institutions should ensure that online learning platforms are equipped with robust, user-friendly features that facilitate interactive and engaging learning experiences. Invest in high-speed internet access and technical support to address connectivity issues.

2. Promote Inclusivity and Accessibility:

- Educators should develop strategies to accommodate diverse learning needs and styles. This could involve providing options for synchronous and asynchronous learning, offering various formats, and ensuring that content is accessible to students with disabilities.

3. Foster a Balanced Approach to Learning:

- Institutions should adopt blended or hybrid learning models that combine the strengths of online and offline learning. This approach can offer flexibility while maintaining the benefits of face-to-face interaction.

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